

Mitigating Interference via Spatial and Spectral Nulling: Open Air Experimental Results

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Abstract— Phase only transmit nulling may help the next generation of radar systems operate in an over-crowded RF spectrum. Open air experimental results from an eight-channel X-band radar test bed are presented that demonstrate an approach for generating constant modulus waveforms that possess spatial nulls when transmitted from an antenna array. The Re-iterative Uniform Weight Optimization (RUWO) algorithm is utilized to generate phase only weights using both a deterministic and adaptive approach. The two strategies are compared. The results demonstrate that RUWO can be used to create spatial nulls and highlight the need for careful calibration of both the transmitter and receiver.

I. INTRODUCTION

High power and possibly wideband radar systems cause interference for users operating in overlapping regions of the increasingly crowded RF spectrum. It is possible to partially mitigate this interference using spatial or frequency nulling; several techniques have been developed using constant modulus signals [1-6].

This work presents open air experimental results demonstrating spatial nulling via the Re-Iterative Uniform Weight Optimization (RUWO) algorithm. RUWO generates constant modulus radar waveforms with spatial, frequency, or space-frequency nulls for MIMO transmit arrays by utilizing the maximum signal-to-interference plus noise ratio (SINR) framework in a re-iterative fashion [1]. RUWO requires either a deterministic interference model or actual measured interference to construct phase only nulling weights. Measured interference can be used adaptively in a closed loop configuration to overcome antenna calibration errors that may complicate modeling of received interference. Experiments were performed to assess the performance of the RUWO algorithm for both the deterministic and adaptive approaches. Experimental results were obtained using the Naval Research Laboratory's Space Time Adaptive Nulling (STAN) radar test bed, an eight-channel X-band MIMO system.

A brief overview of the RUWO algorithm is given in Section II and the eight-channel X-band MIMO test bed is described in Section III. The procedure used to calibrate the recently constructed eight-channel receiver is detailed in Section IV. Open air experimental results using the full eight channels of the X-band test bed are presented in Section V and the paper concludes in Section VI.

II. RE-ITERATIVE UNIFORM WEIGHT OPTIMIZATION (RUWO) ALGORITHM

RUWO is a general construct that can be used to generate phase only weights for various applications; here it is used to produce spatial nulls. A more complete formulation for spatial, frequency, or space-frequency nulling may be found in [1].

Let

$$\mathbf{v}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d\sin\theta} & \dots & e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d(M-1)\sin\theta} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (1)$$

denote a length- M spatial steering vector where θ is the desired steering angle and d is the element spacing and let \mathbf{R} denote the $M \times M$ interference covariance matrix. The covariance matrix may be defined deterministically as

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{q}\mathbf{q}^H + \delta\mathbf{I} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d\sin\phi} & \dots & e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d(M-1)\sin\phi} \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad (3)$$

ϕ is the angle of the interference source, and $\delta\mathbf{I}$ is a diagonal loading term. The covariance matrix can also be calculated adaptively from received data as

$$\mathbf{R} = \left(\frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=1}^P \mathbf{y}_p \mathbf{y}_p^H \right) + \delta\mathbf{I} \quad (4)$$

in which \mathbf{y}_p is the p^{th} $M \times 1$ snapshot of received data on the array, P is the number of snapshots used to compute the covariance matrix, and $(\bullet)^*$ denotes complex conjugation. In (4) δ is set to the receiver noise power. The phase-only RUWO solution is computed iteratively as

This work was sponsored by the Office of Naval Research Base Program and the Radar Division of the Naval Research Laboratory.

$$\mathbf{v}_k = \exp(j\angle(\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{v}_{k-1})) \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{v}_k is the k^{th} iteration and \mathbf{v}_0 is given in (1). The complete set of transmitted waveforms is expressed as

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{s}\mathbf{v}_k^T \quad (6)$$

in which the m^{th} column of \mathbf{S} corresponds to the waveform transmitted from the m^{th} element of the array and \mathbf{s} is the length- N discretized radar waveform.

III. SPACE TIME ADAPTIVE NULLING (STAN) RADAR TEST BED

The Space Time Adaptive Nulling (STAN) radar test bed consists of an eight-channel X-band transmitter and receiver as well as a dipole antenna array. The antenna array, shown in Figure 1, consists of 18 cards and each card contains a sub-array of 32 dipole antennas stacked vertically with a single corporate feed. Each card can be controlled independently allowing up to 18 independent elements in azimuth however, in this paper only eight cards are used. The spacing between dipoles is a half-inch in both azimuth and elevation. The transmitter is an eight-channel vector signal generator.

Figure 1. Front (left) and back (right) of the 32×18 dipole antenna array

Each channel of the transmitter consists of a 16-bit in-phase and quadrature arbitrary waveform generator with a sample rate of 150 MS/s and a two-stage vector up-conversion chain to 9.9 GHz.

The analog portion of the receiver has eight channels, each containing a two-stage down conversion to an intermediate frequency (IF) of 50 MHz. The bandwidth at the IF is 20 MHz. A 16-bit eight-channel digital receiver with a sampling rate of 200 MS/s is used to capture the output of the analog receiver. The system also contains a 2 W power amplifier for each transmit channel, a circulator and blanking switch to protect each channel of the receiver, and an FPGA for generating trigger pulses. Many of the system components can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Annotated picture of the eight-channel transmitter and receiver

IV. EIGHT-CHANNEL RECEIVER CALIBRATION

Calibration of the eight-channel receiver is accomplished through the use of least-squares (LS) based filters derived from collected data.

The data used for calibration is collected systematically by transmitting a pulse from one channel of the transmitter into a two-way splitter. Data is first collected with port one connected to receiver channel one and port two connected to channels two through eight for a total of seven data collects. Each port of the splitter is connected to one receiver channel by a unique cable that is later used to connect the system to the corresponding element of the antenna array; as a result, the characteristics of each cable are compensated for in the calibration.

Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_{1,k} &= e^{j\phi_k} \mathbf{s}_t * \mathbf{h}_1 * \mathbf{r}_1 \\ \mathbf{y}_k &= e^{j\phi_k} \mathbf{s}_t * \mathbf{h}_2 * \mathbf{r}_k \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_{1,k}$ is the time domain data received on channel one from port one of the splitter, \mathbf{y}_k is the data received on the k^{th} channel from port two, \mathbf{s}_t is the pulse transmitted into the splitter, \mathbf{h}_1 and \mathbf{h}_2 are respectively the impulse responses of ports one and two of the splitter, \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_k are respectively the impulse responses of receiver channels one and k , and $k=2, \dots, 8$ is the channel received during the data collect along with channel one. The phase ϕ_k is associated with the trigger delay and may be unique for every data collect; it is the same in both $\mathbf{y}_{1,k}$ and \mathbf{y}_k , which are collected at the same time.

Next, data is collected by connecting port one of the splitter to receiver channel two and port two of the splitter to receiver channel one, again using the appropriate cable to connect each receiver channel as in the previous data collects. Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_1 &= e^{j\theta_1} \mathbf{s}_t * \mathbf{h}_2 * \mathbf{r}_1 \\ \mathbf{z}_2 &= e^{j\theta_1} \mathbf{s}_t * \mathbf{h}_1 * \mathbf{r}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{z}_1 is the time domain data received on channel one from port two of the splitter and \mathbf{z}_2 is the data received on channel two from port one of the splitter. As in (7), the phase θ_1 is associated with the trigger delay and is the same in both \mathbf{z}_1 and \mathbf{z}_2 , which are collected at the same time.

Channels two through eight are calibrated through two repeated applications of LS, first to make \mathbf{y}_k look like $\mathbf{y}_{1,k}$ for $k=2, \dots, 8$ and then to make $\mathbf{y}_{1,1}$ look like the ideal waveform filtered and zero-padded $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}$. It is assumed that the transmitter has already been calibrated and consequently there is very little difference between \mathbf{s}_t and $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}$ before zero-padding.

The first length M LS calibration filter has the form

$$\mathbf{w}_k = (\mathbf{Y}_k^H \mathbf{Y}_k)^{-1} \mathbf{Y}_k^H \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{1,k} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mathbf{Y}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_k(0) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \mathbf{y}_k(0) & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{y}_k(N-1) & \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{y}_k(N-1) & \ddots & \mathbf{y}_k(0) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \mathbf{y}_k(N-1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

is a Toeplitz matrix containing shifted and zero-padded versions of the data received on the k^{th} channel, \mathbf{y}_k , and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{1,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor - 1}^T & \mathbf{y}_{1,k}^T & \mathbf{0}_{\lceil \frac{M}{2} \rceil}^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

is the zero-padded data received on channel one in which $\mathbf{0}_{\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor - 1}$ and $\mathbf{0}_{\lceil \frac{M}{2} \rceil}$ are $\left(\left\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \right\rfloor - 1\right) \times 1$ and $\left\lceil \frac{M}{2} \right\rceil \times 1$ vectors of zeros, respectively ($\lfloor \bullet \rfloor$ is the floor operator and $\lceil \bullet \rceil$ is the ceiling operator). The resulting filters \mathbf{w}_k are applied to data received on channels $k=2, \dots, 8$.

The second length M LS calibration filter has the form

$$\mathbf{w}_0 = (\mathbf{Y}_{1,2}^H \mathbf{Y}_{1,2})^{-1} \mathbf{Y}_{1,2}^H \tilde{\mathbf{s}} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{Y}_{1,2}^H$ is a Toeplitz matrix containing shifted and zero-padded versions of the data, $\mathbf{y}_{1,2}$, received on channel one at the same time that \mathbf{y}_2 was received on channel two and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{s}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor - 1}^T & \mathbf{s}^T & \mathbf{0}_{\lceil \frac{M}{2} \rceil - 1}^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

is the zero-padded version of the filtered ideal waveform \mathbf{s} . The resulting filter \mathbf{w}_0 is likewise applied to all data received on channels $k=2, \dots, 8$ after application of \mathbf{w}_k .

Channel one is calibrated by applying a single tap filter followed by the previously described filter \mathbf{w}_0 . The single tap filter is calculated from the data received on channel one from splitter port one $\mathbf{y}_{1,2}$, the data received on channel two from port two \mathbf{y}_2 , the data received on channel one from port two \mathbf{z}_1 , and the data received on channel two from port one \mathbf{z}_2 . This filter has the form

$$\mathbf{w}_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\overline{\mathbf{y}_{1,2} \mathbf{z}_2}}{\overline{\mathbf{y}_2 \mathbf{z}_1}}} \quad (14)$$

where $\overline{\bullet}$ is the mean operator and the resulting filter \mathbf{w}_1 will have the effect of making the data received on channel one from splitter port two look like it was received on channel one from port one.

The transmitter is calibrated using a single phase and amplitude weight for each channel. This weight is determined using an X-band oscilloscope to collect data from channel one paired with channels two through eight similar to the procedure for calibrating the receiver.

V. OPEN AIR EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Open air experiments were conducted using the STAN test bed on the rooftop of a building. The rooftop had substantial features and metal trim resulting in a high multipath environment. The transmitted radar waveform consisted of a 10 μs pulsed sinusoid with a center frequency of 9.9 GHz. A horn antenna with 27 dBi of gain was placed on the adjacent rooftop approximately 100 ft from the radar antenna. This second antenna served two purposes: 1.) To act as an interference source by transmitting a continuous wave signal at 9.9 GHz and 2.) To measure the power transmitted from the radar.

After calibrating the transmitter and receiver, an identical waveform was transmitted from each of the eight antenna elements. The horn antenna on the adjacent rooftop was connected to a spectrum analyzer and the received power was measured at several azimuth angles as the radar antenna was rotated. Figure 3 compares the pattern measured at the horn antenna to the ideal pattern for the eight element linear array.

Figure 3. Comparison of measured and ideal quiescent antenna patterns

The measured pattern is in good agreement with the ideal pattern indicating adequate calibration of the transmitter. The discrepancies between the measured and ideal patterns in Fig. 3 are consistent with a high multipath environment.

The goal of the experimental campaign was to assess the ability of the RUWO algorithm to determine a phase only weight vector that produces a spatial null at a desired angle. The interference covariance matrix within the RUWO construct can be computed adaptively by measuring the interference or deterministically by modeling the interference. The performance of RUWO will be characterized by examining the nulled antenna patterns resulting from both the adaptive and deterministic approaches.

The horn antenna was used to transmit a continuous wave signal at 9.9 GHz. The radar antenna was rotated such that the incidence angle of the interference was 10° , 25° , and 50° from boresight. A $100 \mu\text{s}$ segment of the interference signal was recorded by the radar receiver for each of the three angles and subsequently used to calculate an adaptive interference covariance matrix within the RUWO framework. For each of the three angles a phase only weight vector was generated using the adaptive approach in (4) and the deterministic approach in (2). For both approaches 50 iterations of (5) were used and in the adaptive approach the entire $100 \mu\text{s}$ data record was used in forming the covariance matrix.

After determining the phase only weight vectors, the weights are applied digitally to the transmitter and the patterns are again measured with the horn antenna and spectrum analyzer. In each case, the measured patterns are compared to the predicted RUWO pattern, computed under the assumption that the weights are applied to an ideal linear array.

Figures 4-6 display the measured and predicted patterns when the adaptive RUWO weights are computed from the interference recorded at 10° , 25° , and 50° , respectively. The measured quiescent pattern is provided to indicate the depth of the null relative to the power transmitted without spatial nulling. The mainbeam null at 10° (Fig. 4) performs well, however the mainlobe is deflected as expected and the null is shifted to 11° . The 25° and 50° cases (Figs. 5 and 6) exhibit an even worse shift in the null locations to 29° and 56° , respectively. The measured RUWO pattern in the 50° case deviates significantly from the predicted RUWO pattern away from the mainlobe.

Figure 4. Comparison of the measured quiescent, measured Adaptive RUWO, and predicted Adaptive RUWO antenna patterns for interference at 10°

Figure 5. Comparison of the measured quiescent, measured Adaptive RUWO, and predicted Adaptive RUWO antenna patterns for interference at 25°

Figure 6. Comparison of the measured quiescent, measured Adaptive RUWO, and predicted Adaptive RUWO antenna patterns for interference at 50°

Figure 8. Comparison of the measured quiescent, measured Deterministic RUWO, and predicted Deterministic RUWO antenna patterns for interference at 25°

The deterministic RUWO results for the three cases are shown in Figures 7-9. Again the 10° (Fig. 7) case performs well, and experiences a slight shift to 11° . In the 25° scenario (Fig. 8) the null is shifted to 22° , compared to 29° for the adaptive case. As in the adaptive case, the measured RUWO pattern in the 50° null case (Fig. 9) has the most distortion relative to the predicted RUWO pattern. In this case the null is shifted to 58° . Note that for all three angles the null is always deeper when the adaptive approach is employed.

Figure 7. Comparison of the measured quiescent, measured Deterministic RUWO, and predicted Deterministic RUWO antenna patterns for interference at 10°

Figure 9. Comparison of the measured quiescent, measured Deterministic RUWO, and predicted Deterministic RUWO antenna patterns for interference at 50°

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Radar systems can employ transmit nulling schemes to avoid interfering with other nearby RF users. The RUWO algorithm provides a construct for determining constant modulus weights that produce a spatial null on transmit. Computing the weights requires either a deterministic model of the interference or a measurement of the actual interference source. The Naval Research Laboratory's Space Time Adaptive Nulling (STAN) radar test bed was used to experimentally assess the performance of the RUWO algorithm. The STAN test bed consists of eight transmit and receive channels which are carefully calibrated using a least-squares based technique.

Experimental results were obtained for three different interference angles. These results indicate that RUWO can be effectively used to generate spatial nulls using constant modulus weights. For both the adaptive and deterministic approaches, the measured null appeared offset in azimuth angle relative to the desired null location. This phenomenon appeared to be worse for nulls that were further from the mainlobe of the antenna pattern. It is unclear if this effect is due to transmitter and receiver calibration errors, antenna calibration errors, or the multipath environment where the test was conducted. The adaptive approach yielded nulls that were deeper than those obtained using the deterministic approach.

Future work will include tests in an anechoic chamber, field tests with multiple interference sources, and development of improved transmitter calibration techniques. The effect of power amplifier saturation on spatial nulling and the generation of space-frequency nulls will also be investigated.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Higgins, T. Webster, and A. K. Shackelford, "Mitigating Interference via Spatial and Spectral Nulls," in *Radar 2012*, Glasgow, UK, October 2012.
- [2] M. R. Cook, T. Higgins, A. K. Shackelford. "Thinned spectrum radar waveforms," *2010 International Waveform Diversity and Design Conference*, pp. 238-243 (2010).
- [3] D. A. Day. "Fast phase-only pattern nulling for large phased array antennas," *IEEE Transactions on 2009 IEEE Radar Conference*, pp. 1-4 (2009).
- [4] K. Gerlach. "Thinned spectrum ultrawideband waveforms using stepped-frequency polyphase codes," *Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 1356-1361 (1998).
- [5] I. W. Selesnick, S. U. Pillai, R. Zheng. "An iterative algorithm for the construction of notched chirp signals," *IEEE Transactions on 2010 IEEE Radar Conference*, pp. 200-203 (2010).
- [6] I. W. Selesnick, S. U. Pillai. "Chirp-like transmit waveforms with multiple frequency-notches," *2011 IEEE Radar Conference*, pp. 1106 - 1110 (2011).